

Deliverable D2.5 Report on the outreach activities and training activities produced

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Log of changes

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20/07/2023	0v4	Patricia Palagi (SIB)	MB comments addressed
20/07/2023	1v0	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version to be uploaded into EC Portal

¹<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1dczelq-a3iiwmqNC9x6Oc1N5lXuwxhnh6yejOe5qXb0/edit?usp=sharing>

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1. Executive Summary

The scope of deliverable D2.5, part of ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2 Task 2.4, is to provide an overview of the data management and stewardship related training and outreach activities that have been undertaken during the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project.

ELIXIR-CONVERGE aimed to enhance Europe's data management capacity through an extensive training program implemented across the European Research Area. When ELIXIR-CONVERGE was initiated, there was a significant gap in research data management (RDM) and the need to advocate for their effective application. ELIXIR had almost 22 Nodes and had attracted interest from various European and non-European countries. Additionally, ELIXIR had expanded its Communities from four to sixteen.

To assist these countries and Communities in adopting best practices in data management from the outset, a range of outreach activities were developed, and are described in this report. These activities aimed to disseminate information on data management plans (DMPs), their applications, and best practices. The target audiences identified included principal investigators, university libraries, national and local research data management communities, bioinformatics core facilities, industry stakeholders, funders, and policymakers. The objectives of Task 6.4 were to raise awareness

about the importance of DMPs and to strengthen connections between ELIXIR and expert networks, and key partners such as ESFRI RI and EOSC.

All these activities focused on three primary categories of stakeholders: 1) prospective countries interested in joining ELIXIR, 2) ELIXIR Communities, and 3) national and local research data management networks. By targeting these prioritised stakeholders individually or in groups, ELIXIR-CONVERGE aimed to effectively address data management challenges and foster collaboration and knowledge sharing in key DM areas.

Distinguishing between training and dissemination activities can sometimes be challenging, as overlaps or blurred boundaries between both may exist. In the context of ELIXIR-CONVERGE, we defined training as any event that enables participants to learn something new or improve their skills. Training activities, which thus complement the outreach activities, were also conducted in prospective ELIXIR Member countries and for new Communities, not only to build capacity and engagement but also to expand outreach efforts, and ensure that the project outputs are visible, useful and hence impactful. These activities are reported in the companion [deliverable 2.2](#).²

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	No
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	Yes
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No

²https://docs.google.com/document/d/1WDPM6YEsV3W2sJcCkAR_spBBiqZsaLf6zBBH7Vazygg/edit

Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	Yes
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	Yes
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	No
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	No
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	No
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	No
Key Result 3.4: Enable ‘FAIR at source’ practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	No
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No

<p>Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Introduction

ELIXIR-CONVERGE was set to strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area. The gap in training in research data management had been widely acknowledged when the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project started, including in an ELIXIR Implementation Study³: Towards Data Stewardship in ELIXIR: Training & Portal.

Indeed, when the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project was initiated, there was a clear need for training researchers on research data management skills and advocating for the urgency and need to apply those skills effectively. ELIXIR counted 21 Nodes at that time, and several European (e.g. Austria, Poland, Slovakia), and non-European countries (e.g. Australia, Canada and South Africa), had shown interest in joining ELIXIR. In addition, ELIXIR has since then continuously established new Communities, starting with four and growing to 16 today.

To help these countries and Communities onboard and adopt best practices in Data Management from the start, a set of outreach activities was developed to disseminate information about DMP, its applications and best practices. These activities targeted audiences complementary to Tasks 2.2 and 2.3. such as principal investigators (PIs), university libraries, national and local RDM communities, bioinformatics core facilities, industry, funders and policymakers. These activities aimed to raise awareness of the need for DMP and strengthen the links between ELIXIR, the expert networks (WP1 and national networks) and key partners such as ESFRI RI and EOSC. Training activities, as defined in Task 2.2 and Task 2.3, were run in prospective ELIXIR Member countries and for new Communities to not only develop capacity and engagement, but also to outreach.

The overall objective of ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2 was to build a comprehensive, interconnected and sustainable ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, in line with Objective 2 ([Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area](#)). The training activities in Task 2.2 and 2.3 aimed to target researchers and data stewards across all ELIXIR Nodes and develop and deliver a set of foundational ELIXIR Data Management courses. Task 2.4, the scope of this deliverable, focused thus on outreaching prospective audiences susceptible to adopting best practices in data management and bridging existing local and national networks across Europe and ELIXIR.

³ <https://elixir-europe.org/internal-projects/commissioned-services/towards-data-stewardship>

Relationship with other WPs

ELIXIR-CONVERGE aimed to connect the distributed local support for data management across Europe, using international standards and best practices. The three main pillars that made this possible were: 1) the people - the network of life science data management professionals (WP1); 2) a shared toolkit - RMDkit, which concentrated the different tools and best practices under one single instrument (WP3); and 3) the skills and training, which were the drivers of the DM Training Programme set up in WP2 train and raise awareness about data management skills (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: ELIXIR-CONVERGE resources network for data management (image from [Deliverable D2.1](#)⁴ Report on identified training needs and a timeline for training courses)

WP2 Training and Capacity Building enables the different WPs to translate their efforts into training and outreach about activities that enhance both the end products and the capacity of their expertise. Specifically:

- WP2 has worked with WP1 Data Management Experts network to reach out to national and local networks, to communicate about the tools developed in the project, and exchange information and best practices in DM, and to co-create training and outreach materials.
- WP2 has worked with WP3 to align the training work related to the RDMKit. WP2 participated in WP3 contentathons, established the training links and data steward roles in the RDMkit, and contributed to disseminating the information about the RDMkit and the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW), among others.
- WP2 has worked with WP4 to organise events and to create dissemination materials targeted to prospective countries, ELIXIR Communities, and new target audiences.
- WP2 has assisted WP5 in establishing use-case training, and disseminating best practices in DM.

⁴<https://zenodo.org/record/4892863#.YN2mdpNKj0o>

These collaborations will continue beyond the end of ELIXIR-CONVERGE in the recently created ELIXIR Research Data Management Community. This community will bring together the expertise, experience, people, tools and knowledge in DMP, gathered together in this project, and thus ensure the work developed in ELIXIR-CONVERGE will continue.

4. Description of work accomplished

The work that has been accomplished during the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project to outreach about ELIXIR, best practices in data management, and the need for data management plans, consisted of webinars, presentations, meetings, and the development of materials.

In this deliverable, we describe some of the outreach and dissemination activities (presentations, webinars etc.) dealt by WP2, and fully reported in the ELIXIR-CONVERGE [Dissemination spreadsheet](#)⁵. On the other hand, the training and training materials for courses and workshops developed during the project are reported in the companion [Deliverable 2.2](#)⁶.

These activities targeted several prioritised stakeholders, individually or in groups, that fall within three main categories: 1) prospective countries interested to join ELIXIR; 2) ELIXIR Communities; and 3) national and local RDM networks.

4.1 Webinars

Short online seminars served as an invaluable means to engage with a wide range of participants, reflecting the primary objective of maximising outreach. The significance of these events was particularly accentuated by the prevailing COVID-19 situation, which necessitated the adoption of virtual platforms for knowledge exchange. ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2 partners, along with valuable contributions from other WP collaborators, successfully organised at least 18 webinars online. These webinars encompassed diverse topics, including data management, open access, biocuration, data management plans and policies, the professionalisation of data stewardship roles, and the RDMkit. Beyond their educational aspect, these webinars also served as an excellent opportunity to showcase the achievements and activities of ELIXIR, thereby raising awareness about the organisation and its invaluable contributions.

The webinars attracted various audiences, ranging from bioinformaticians and life science researchers to project managers and research infrastructure operators. Notably, one of the webinars organised by ELIXIR Israel specifically targeted policymakers, providing them with crucial insights into the significance of data management. Additionally, a webinar organised by WP3 reached out to EOSC-Life, further fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange within the scientific community. Demonstrating a commitment to global engagement, two events were specifically tailored to audiences in India and Latin America, transcending European geographical boundaries. These efforts

⁵https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1OGNHLElusi99BpT63NGeh_qRY9cMpKUBmVEGjoiLumQ/edit#gid=1159678595

⁶https://docs.google.com/document/d/1WDPM6YEsV3W2sJcCkAR_spBBiqZsaLf6zBBH7Vazygg/edit

exemplify the inclusive nature of the webinars, effectively disseminating knowledge and establishing connections beyond regional borders.

4.2 Meetings

Several online or in-person meetings were organised, particularly targeting prospective countries interested in joining ELIXIR and new ELIXIR Communities. A series of virtual outreach events⁷ for Romanian scientists was organised in September and October 2020 in tasks T4.3 and T2.4. In one of these events, Balint Balint (ELIXIR Hungary) presented an overview of ELIXIR Hungary, the provision of training in ELIXIR, and in particular training in data management.

For the ICRI⁸ conference (International Conference on Research Infrastructure) in 2021, we planned to hold parallel bioinformatics training workshops where DM and Data Stewardship and the ELIXIR experience were the focus. However, the meeting was held online due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and the workshops were cancelled. Nevertheless, ELIXIR and ELIXIR-CONVERGE were represented by Andrew Smith (WP4), who participated in a round table on "International data management policies and practices".

ELIXIR Portugal colleagues Daniel Faria and Jorge Oliveira delivered the "Introduction to Data Management Plans" course of the "Ready for BioData Management?" program to ELIXIR Cyprus, an ELIXIR Node observer. For several of the Estonian courses on data management, Latvia members were also invited to attend. These are four illustrations of events targeting non-ELIXIR Nodes.

Most of the ELIXIR Nodes have seen national and local RDM networks bloom. Several Nodes organised national events to exchange information and best practices and showcase the ELIXIR-CONVERGE partners' data management and stewardship experiences. An example is the collaboration with the ELIXIR-NL [Data Stewards Interest Group](#)⁹ (DSIG) - an internationally established community hub for data stewardship enabling informal and inclusive knowledge and experience exchange, in which various ELIXIR Nodes participate on a regular basis, and ELIXIR-LU and EE even co-chaired a session.

The complete list of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE outreach events is available in the [Dissemination spreadsheet](#)¹⁰. The videos, flyers and course materials developed in the context of these activities are also linked in the Dissemination spreadsheet. The resulting training materials are findable in the ELIXIR Training Portal TeSS and reusable for future use. The other materials are findable on the ELIXIR website.

⁷<https://elixir-europe.org/events/webinar-elixir-romania>

⁸ <http://icri2021.ca/>

⁹<https://www.dtls.nl/about/community/interest-groups/data-stewards-interest-group/>

¹⁰https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1OGNHLElusi99BpT63NGeh_qRY9cMpKUBmVEGjolLumQ/edit#gid=1159678595

4.3 Development of materials

Two Train-the-Trainer (TtT) events were conducted, following the successful format of the regular ELIXIR-GOBLET TtT of the Training Programme (TrP). These events included insightful discussions on the challenges associated with teaching Data Management/Data Stewardship (DM/DS). The key takeaway from these discussions was that the pedagogical challenges in teaching DM/DS topics are minimal, as the content is relatively straightforward. However, the real obstacles lie in motivating researchers to actually participate in DM/DS courses and overcoming their lack of enthusiasm or resistance towards investing time in understanding how to make data FAIR.

Based on the conclusions drawn from these discussions and survey, an important project was initiated: the creation of a video aimed at raising awareness. This initiative, detailed in the accompanying [deliverable D2.2](#)¹¹, aims to address the challenge of motivating researchers and convincing them of the significance and necessity of DM/DS courses. By showcasing the importance of data management in a compelling visual format, the video endeavours to engage researchers who may initially lack enthusiasm for the topic and highlight the value and relevance of these courses.

In addition to materials developed in the context of the events above, several Task 2.4 and WP2 members spent much effort producing an RDM and DMP video to raise awareness of principal investigators of the importance of having data management plans. All Task 2.4 members, and several WP3 members, contributed to the design of the scripts for the video, the edition and review, and the dissemination.

Overall, these TtT events and subsequent discussions have shed light on the importance of addressing the motivational aspect of DM/DS training and have led to the development of an impactful video campaign to emphasise the need for proper data management practices.

¹¹https://docs.google.com/document/d/1WDPM6YEsV3W2sJcCkAR_spBBiqZsaLf6zBBH7Vazygg/edit

Figure 2: ELIXIR-CONVERGE resources network for data management ([video](#) hosted on YouTube¹², and linked in [TeSS](#)¹³)

4.4 Other dissemination activities

Another notable action of the WP2 members has been developing and promoting the RDMkit and the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) at national levels. One of the key objectives of WP2 was to establish seamless connections between the RDMkit, which was developed in WP3, and the pertinent training events and resources available on TeSS. The intention behind this initiative was to ensure that visitors exploring the RDMkit pages could navigate to training materials that would be relevant and beneficial to them. In pursuing this goal, the WP2 members have played a significant role in disseminating information about the RDMkit during their courses and seminars. Their efforts have extended beyond educational settings, as they have actively communicated about the RDMkit to academic and national institutions, firmly establishing it as the preferred tool for research data management among a wider audience.

The Community of Practice (CoP) of RDM Trainers Network emerged as an important outcome of this project, serving as a collaborative platform to foster knowledge sharing and skills development in Research Data Management (RDM). With a strong emphasis on outreach and dissemination efforts, the Network has propagated the importance of RDM practices and facilitated the exchange of best practices in the broader ELIXIR RDM Community.

One of the essential responsibilities of several WP2 members is to provide comprehensive national support and guidance to researchers in their respective countries regarding data management tools. Through dedicated initiatives and programs, the WP2 members ensure that researchers can access the necessary resources and knowledge to manage their data effectively. By facilitating national-level support, the WP2 members contribute significantly to the overall improvement of research data management practices on a broader scale.

¹² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=S7HfUe1hWcg>

¹³ <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/materials/elixir-converge-the-why-of-research-data-management>

For the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW), for instance, ELIXIR Switzerland has dedicated considerable efforts to create a Swiss DSW instance and to showcase the capabilities and benefits of this tool to researchers attending training courses in Switzerland. Similarly, ELIXIR Slovenia has updated the Slovenian DSW instance and showcased it to researchers at different classes and educational events in Slovenia.

Finally, during the last ELIXIR All-Hand Meeting (June 2023), WP2 members organised a workshop to find the learning gaps and training needs on FAIR and data management across ELIXIR Nodes and Communities.

5. Results

5.1 Attendance of events

Throughout the duration of ELIXIR-CONVERGE, 19 outreach events were organised either by WP2 or in collaboration with other project members. These events served as platforms for knowledge dissemination on data management and engagement with communities. More than 500 individuals participated in these webinars, highlighting the significant impact and reach of the project.

Additionally, over the course of the project, more than 150 presentations and workshops were organised, all incorporating an outreach component. These gatherings attracted a diverse audience, with a collective attendance of over 5000 people. These numbers do not include the participation in the training courses. The training events are reported in the companion [deliverable D2.2](#)¹⁴.

5.1 Usage and dissemination of materials developed

Although the [video](#)¹⁵ to raise researchers' awareness of the need for data management was released only a month ago, it was already shown in several outreach contexts. For instance, it was displayed during the course on Data Management taught by ELIXIR Portugal colleagues, organised under the ELIXIR auspices for the X-Meeting. The X-Meeting is the Brazilian bioinformatics annual conference in Curitiba, Brazil early June 2023. The video has been visualised over 540 times on YouTube and is also available on [TeSS](#)¹⁶. In the future, we will continue to show this video in presentations and courses.

The complete list of training materials with an outreach component that can be reused can be found in [TeSS](#)¹⁷ as well. Altogether, the videos were seen over 1000 times.

¹⁴https://docs.google.com/document/d/1WDPM6YEsV3W2sJcCkAR_spBBiqZsaLf6zBBH7Vazygg/edit

¹⁵<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=S7HfUe1hWcg>

¹⁶<https://tess.elixir-europe.org/materials/elixir-converge-the-why-of-research-data-management>

¹⁷<https://tess.elixir-europe.org/search?q=ELIXIR-CONVERGE>

6. Conclusions

WP2's main objective is educating and raising awareness regarding Research Data Management (RDM) practices. The overarching goal is to empower individuals involved in various projects and work domains to enhance the quality of their research endeavours. Through a comprehensive and dynamic range of outreach activities, as highlighted in this report, the ELIXIR Nodes participating in WP2 have demonstrated their commitment to advancing RDM practices. These efforts are not limited to the scope of ELIXIR-CONVERGE but are loomed to have a sustainable impact within ELIXIR, the newly created ELIXIR RDM community and national communities, extending far beyond the project's timeline. The WP2 Task 2.4 activities helped to foster a culture of adoption of effective RDM strategies, creating a lasting legacy that will continue to positively influence research practices across diverse scientific communities.

7. Impact

The outreach events highlighted in this deliverable, along with the impactful presentations and workshops, underscore the profound influence of ELIXIR-CONVERGE in disseminating invaluable knowledge on data management and fostering collaborations within the research community across Europe and beyond its borders. These initiatives have successfully contributed to strengthening connections between ELIXIR Nodes and national data management and data stewardship networks. While the exact impact on the increasing number of these networks cannot be precisely determined, it is evident that ELIXIR-CONVERGE and its associated outreach and training activities have played a significant role in initiating or reinforcing these connections.

ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2 has successfully facilitated synergies and collaborations not only within the project itself but also extending beyond its boundaries (Figure 1). The Community of Practice (CoP) stands as a prime example of these synergies, solidifying its position as a cornerstone of expertise in research data management within the ELIXIR network. Through the concerted efforts of ELIXIR-CONVERGE, valuable collaborations and partnerships have been forged, contributing to the collective advancement of research data management practices.

8. Next Steps

The ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2 community has contributed to establishing various mechanisms, including the development of reusable outreach and training materials, the formation of the Community of Practice (CoP), and the implementation of the ELITMa program. These and other WP2 remarkable outputs will continue to thrive and expand within the newly created ELIXIR RDM Community. The active involvement of numerous ELIXIR Nodes has played a pivotal role in establishing national and local networks of RDM and Data Stewards, ensuring the continued utilisation of the resources that have been created along the project.

The ELIXIR RDM Community will serve as a vital platform to continue nurturing the outputs of this project. This community objectives are to:

- Facilitate the exchange of knowledge and best practices among RDM trainers.

- Foster the development and FAIRification of RDM training materials to promote their reuse and adoption by ELIXIR Nodes.
- Design RDM learning paths tailored for researchers, data stewards, tool developers, and trainers.
- Sustain ongoing outreach efforts to emphasise the significance and requirements of effective data management plans and practices.

Through the collaborative efforts within the ELIXIR RDM Community, we aim to advance the field of research data management, empower individuals with essential skills, and ensure the widespread adoption of best practices across the research community.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable.

